

**ON SETS OF INTEGERS WHICH ARE BOTH SUM-FREE AND
PRODUCT-FREE**

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Abstract

We consider sets of positive integers containing no sum of two elements in the set and also no product of two elements. We show that the upper density of such a set is strictly smaller than $\frac{1}{2}$ and that this is best possible. Further, we also find the maximal order for the density of such sets that are also periodic modulo some positive integer.

1. Introduction

If \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} are sets of integers, we let $\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{B}$ denote the set of sums $a + b$ with $a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}$, and we let $\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{B}$ denote the set of products ab with $a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}$. The sum-product problem in combinatorial number theory is to show that if \mathcal{A} is a finite set of positive integers, then either $\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}$ or $\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}$ is a much larger set than \mathcal{A} . Specifically, Erdős and Szemerédi [2] conjecture that if $\epsilon > 0$ is arbitrary and \mathcal{A} is a set of N positive integers, then for N sufficiently large depending on the choice of ϵ , we have

$$|\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}| + |\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}| \geq N^{2-\epsilon}.$$

This conjecture is motivated by the cases when either $|\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}|$ or $|\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}|$ is unusually small. For example, if $\mathcal{A} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, then $\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}$ is small, namely, $|\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}| < 2N$. However, $\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}$ is large since there is some $c > 0$ such that $|\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}| > N^2/(\log N)^c$.

And if $\mathcal{A} = \{1, 2, 4, \dots, 2^{N-1}\}$, then $|\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}| < 2N$, but $|\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}| > N^2/2$. The best that we currently know towards this conjecture is that it holds with exponent $4/3$ in the place of 2, a result of Solymosi [8]. (In fact, Solymosi proves this when \mathcal{A} is a set of positive real numbers.)

In this paper we consider a somewhat different question: how dense can \mathcal{A} be if both $\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}$ have no elements in common with \mathcal{A} ? If $\mathcal{A} \cap (\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}) = \emptyset$ we say that \mathcal{A} is sum-free and if $\mathcal{A} \cap (\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}) = \emptyset$ we say \mathcal{A} is product-free. Before stating the main results, we give some background on sets that are either sum-free or product-free.

If $a \in \mathcal{A}$ and \mathcal{A} is sum-free, then $\{a\} + \mathcal{A}$ is disjoint from \mathcal{A} , and so we immediately have that the upper asymptotic density

$$\bar{d}(\mathcal{A}) := \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} |\mathcal{A} \cap [1, n]|$$

is at most $\frac{1}{2}$. Density $\frac{1}{2}$ can be achieved by taking \mathcal{A} as the set of odd natural numbers. Similarly, if \mathcal{A} is a set of residues modulo n and is sum-free, then $D(\mathcal{A}) := |\mathcal{A}|/n$ is at most $\frac{1}{2}$, and this can be achieved when n is even and \mathcal{A} consists of the odd residues. The maximal density for $D(\mathcal{A})$ for \mathcal{A} a sum-free set in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ was considered in [1]. In particular, the maximum for $D(\mathcal{A})$ is $\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{3n}$ if n is divisible solely by primes that are 1 modulo 3, it is $\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3p}$ if n is divisible by some prime that is 2 modulo 3 and p is the least such, and it is $\frac{1}{3}$ otherwise. Consequently, we have $D(\mathcal{A}) \leq \frac{2}{5}$ if \mathcal{A} is a sum-free set in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ and n is odd. It is worth noting that maximal densities of subsets of arbitrary finite abelian groups are determined in [3]. For generalizations to subsets of finite non-abelian groups, see [4].

The problem of the maximum density of product-free sets of positive integers, or of subsets of $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, only recently received attention. For subsets of the positive integers, it was shown in [5] that the upper density of a product-free set must be strictly less than 1, in fact, it cannot exceed $1 - \frac{1}{2a_0}$, where a_0 is the least member of the set. Let $D(n)$ denote the maximum value of $D(\mathcal{A})$ as \mathcal{A} runs over product-free sets in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$. In [7] it was shown that $D(n) < \frac{1}{2}$ for the vast majority of integers, namely for every integer not divisible by the square of a product of 6 distinct primes. Moreover, the density of integers which are divisible by the square of a product of 6 distinct primes was shown to be smaller than 1.56×10^{-8} .

Somewhat surprisingly, $D(n)$ can in fact be arbitrarily close to 1 (see [5]), and thus there are integers n and sets of residues modulo n consisting of 99% of all residues, with the set of pairwise products lying in the remaining 1% of the residues. However, it is not easy to find a numerical example that beats 50%. In [5], an example of a number n with about 1.61×10^8 decimal digits was given with $D(n) > \frac{1}{2}$; it is not known if there are any substantially smaller examples, say with fewer than 10^8 decimal digits.

In [6] the maximal order of $D(n)$ was essentially found: There are positive con-

stants c, C such that for all sufficiently large n , we have

$$D(n) \leq 1 - \frac{c}{(\log \log n)^{1-\frac{c}{2}} \log^2(\log \log \log n)^{1/2}}$$

and there are infinitely many n with

$$D(n) \geq 1 - \frac{C}{(\log \log n)^{1-\frac{c}{2}} \log^2(\log \log \log n)^{1/2}}.$$

In this paper we consider two related questions. First, if \mathcal{A} is a set of integers which is both sum-free and product-free, how large may the upper asymptotic density $\bar{d}(\mathcal{A})$ be? Here a sum-free and product-free set with natural density $\frac{2}{5}$ is achievable by taking

$$\mathcal{A} = \{n : n \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{5}\}.$$

Our first result shows that for a set \mathcal{A} to achieve upper asymptotic density close to $\frac{1}{2}$ it must omit all small integers.

Theorem 1. *Let \mathcal{A} be a set of positive integers that is both product-free and sum-free, and let a_0 be the smallest element of \mathcal{A} . If $\bar{d}(\mathcal{A}) > \frac{2}{5}$, then necessarily*

$$\bar{d}(\mathcal{A}) \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2a_0} \right).$$

Second, set

$$D^*(n) := \max\{D(\mathcal{A}) : \mathcal{A} \text{ is a sum-free, product-free subset of } \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}\}.$$

What is the maximal order of $D^*(n)$? We prove the following complementary results, showing density $\frac{1}{2}$ can be approached, and quantifying the rate of approach.

Theorem 2. *There is a positive constant κ such that for all sufficiently large numbers n ,*

$$D^*(n) \leq \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\kappa}{(\log \log n)^{1-\frac{\kappa}{2}} \log^2(\log \log \log n)^{1/2}}.$$

Theorem 3. *There is a positive constant κ^* and infinitely many integers n with*

$$D^*(n) \geq \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\kappa^*}{(\log \log n)^{1-\frac{\kappa^*}{2}} \log^2(\log \log \log n)^{1/2}}.$$

Note that $D^*(5) = \frac{2}{5}$ and if $5|n$, then $D^*(n) \geq \frac{2}{5}$. A possibly interesting computational problem is to numerically exhibit some n with $D^*(n) > \frac{2}{5}$. Theorem 3 assures us that such numbers exist, but the least example might be very large.

One might also ask for the densest possible set \mathcal{A} for which \mathcal{A} , $\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}$, and $\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}$ are pairwise disjoint. However, Proposition 9 below implies immediately that any sum-free, product-free set $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ with $D(\mathcal{A}) > \frac{2}{5}$ also has $\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{A} \cdot \mathcal{A}$ disjoint. Thus, from Theorem 3, we may have these three sets pairwise disjoint with $D(\mathcal{A})$ arbitrarily close to $\frac{1}{2}$.

2. The Upper Density

Here we prove Theorem 1. We begin with some notation that we use in this section. For a set \mathcal{A} of positive integers and a positive real number x , we write $\mathcal{A}(x)$ for $\mathcal{A} \cap [1, x]$. Set

$$\delta_x := 1 - 2 \frac{|\mathcal{A}(x)|}{x}, \text{ so that } |\mathcal{A}(x)| = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \delta_x)x.$$

Note that $\delta_x \geq 0$ for $|\mathcal{A}(x)| \leq \frac{1}{2}x$. If a is an integer, we write $a + \mathcal{A}$ for $\{a\} + \mathcal{A}$ and we write $a\mathcal{A}$ for $\{a\} \cdot \mathcal{A}$.

Lemma 4. *Suppose that \mathcal{A} is a sum-free set of positive integers and that $a_1, a_2 \in \mathcal{A}$. Then for all $x > 0$,*

$$|(a_1 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_1)) \cap (a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2))| \geq \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3\delta_x) - (a_1 + a_2).$$

Proof. We have the sets $\mathcal{A}(x), a_1 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_1), a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2)$ all lying in $[1, x]$ and the latter two sets are disjoint from the first set (since \mathcal{A} is sum-free). Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} & |(a_1 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_1)) \cap (a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2))| \\ &= |a_1 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_1)| + |a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2)| - |(a_1 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_1)) \cup (a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2))| \\ &\geq |a_1 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_1)| + |a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2)| - (x - |\mathcal{A}(x)|) \\ &\geq (|\mathcal{A}(x)| - a_1) + (|\mathcal{A}(x)| - a_2) + (|\mathcal{A}(x)| - x) = 3|\mathcal{A}(x)| - x - (a_1 + a_2). \end{aligned}$$

But $3|\mathcal{A}(x)| - x = \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3\delta_x)x$, so this completes the proof. \square

For a set \mathcal{A} of positive integers, define the *difference set*

$$\Delta\mathcal{A} := \{a_1 - a_2 : a_1, a_2 \in \mathcal{A}\}.$$

Further, for an integer g , let

$$\mathcal{A}_g := \mathcal{A} \cap (-g + \mathcal{A}) = \{a \in \mathcal{A} : a + g \in \mathcal{A}\}.$$

Corollary 5. *If \mathcal{A} is a sum-free set of positive integers and $g \in \Delta\mathcal{A}$ then, for any $x > 0$,*

$$|\mathcal{A}_g(x)| \geq \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3\delta_x)x + O(1),$$

in which the implied constant depends on both g and \mathcal{A} .

Proof. Suppose that $g \in \Delta\mathcal{A}$, so that there exist $a_1, a_2 \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $a_1 - a_2 = g$. If $a \in \mathcal{A}(x - a_1)$ and $a + a_1 \in a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2)$, then $a + g = a + a_1 - a_2 \in \mathcal{A}$, so that $a \in \mathcal{A}_g$. That is, $\mathcal{A}_g(x - a_1)$ contains $-(a_1 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_1)) \cap (a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2))$. Thus, by Lemma 4,

$$|\mathcal{A}_g(x - a_1)| \geq |(a_1 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_1)) \cap (a_2 + \mathcal{A}(x - a_2))| \geq \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3\delta_x) - (a_1 + a_2),$$

from which the corollary follows. \square

Proposition 6. *If \mathcal{A} is a sum-free set of positive integers with upper density greater than $\frac{2}{5}$, then $\Delta\mathcal{A}$ is the set of all even integers and \mathcal{A} consists solely of odd numbers.*

Proof. We first show that $\Delta\mathcal{A}$ is a subgroup of \mathbb{Z} . Since $\Delta\mathcal{A}$ is closed under multiplication by -1 , it suffices to show that if $g_1, g_2 \in \Delta\mathcal{A}$, then $g_1 + g_2 \in \Delta\mathcal{A}$. If $g_1 + \mathcal{A}_{g_1}$ contains a member a of \mathcal{A}_{g_2} , then $a - g_1 \in \mathcal{A}$ and $a + g_2 \in \mathcal{A}$, so that $g_1 + g_2 \in \Delta\mathcal{A}$. Note that $g_1 + \mathcal{A}_{g_1}$ and \mathcal{A}_{g_2} are both subsets of \mathcal{A} . Now by Corollary 5, if $g_1 + \mathcal{A}_{g_1}$ and \mathcal{A}_{g_2} were disjoint, we would have for each positive real number x ,

$$(1 - 3\delta_x)x + O(1) \leq |\mathcal{A}(x)| = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \delta_x)x,$$

so that $\delta_x \geq \frac{1}{5} + O(\frac{1}{x})$. Hence $\liminf \delta_x \geq \frac{1}{5}$, contradicting the assumption that \mathcal{A} has upper density greater than $\frac{2}{5}$. Thus, $g_1 + \mathcal{A}_{g_1}$ and \mathcal{A}_{g_2} are not disjoint, which as we have seen, implies that $g_1 + g_2 \in \Delta\mathcal{A}$. Thus, $\Delta\mathcal{A}$ is a subgroup of \mathbb{Z} , say $\Delta\mathcal{A} = g\mathbb{Z}$ for some positive integer g .

Since each $a_1 - a_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{g}$ for all $a_1, a_2 \in \mathcal{A}$, all members of \mathcal{A} are in one residue class modulo g . Since \mathcal{A} has upper density greater than $\frac{2}{5}$, it follows that $g = 1$ or 2 . But $\Delta\mathcal{A}$ must be disjoint from \mathcal{A} . Indeed, if $a_1 - a_2 = a_3$ with $a_1, a_2, a_3 \in \mathcal{A}$, then $a_1 = a_2 + a_3$, violating the condition that \mathcal{A} is sum-free. Thus, if $g = 1$, $\mathcal{A} = \emptyset$, and if $g = 2$, \mathcal{A} consists solely of odd numbers. The first case violates our hypothesis, so our proof is complete. \square

Remark 7. Proposition 6 is best possible, as can be seen by taking \mathcal{A} as the set of positive integers that are either 2 or 3 modulo 5.

We now prove the following result which immediately implies Theorem 1.

Proposition 8. *Suppose that \mathcal{A} is a sum-free set of positive integers with least member a_0 . Suppose in addition that $a_0\mathcal{A}$ is disjoint from \mathcal{A} . Then the upper density of \mathcal{A} is at most $\max\{\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}(1 - \frac{1}{2a_0})\}$.*

Proof. If the upper density of \mathcal{A} is at most $\frac{2}{5}$, the result holds trivially, so we may assume the upper density exceeds $\frac{2}{5}$. It follows from Proposition 6 that \mathcal{A} consists solely of odd numbers. Thus, for any real number $x \geq a_0$, both $a_0\mathcal{A}(x/a_0)$ and $\mathcal{A}(x)$ consist solely of odd numbers, they are disjoint, and they lie in $[1, x]$. Thus,

$$|\mathcal{A}(x)| + \left| \mathcal{A}\left(\frac{x}{a_0}\right) \right| = |\mathcal{A}(x)| + \left| a_0\mathcal{A}\left(\frac{x}{a_0}\right) \right| \leq \frac{1}{2}x + O(1).$$

Further $\mathcal{A}(x) \setminus \mathcal{A}(x/a_0)$ is contained within the odd numbers in $(x/a_0, x]$, so that

$$|\mathcal{A}(x)| - \left| \mathcal{A}\left(\frac{x}{a_0}\right) \right| \leq \frac{1}{2}\left(x - \frac{x}{a_0}\right) + O(1).$$

Adding these two inequalities and dividing by 2 gives that $|\mathcal{A}(x)| \leq (\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{4a_0})x + O(1)$, so that \mathcal{A} has upper density at most $\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{4a_0}$, giving the result. \square

3. An Upper Bound for the Density in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$

In this section we prove Theorem 2. We begin by noting the following simple consequence of Proposition 6.

Proposition 9. *Suppose that n is a positive integer and $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ is sum-free. If $D(\mathcal{A}) > \frac{2}{5}$, then n is even and \mathcal{A} is a subset of the odd residues classes in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$.*

Proof. Replace \mathcal{A} with $\bar{\mathcal{A}}$, the set of positive numbers in the residue classes in \mathcal{A} . Then $\bar{\mathcal{A}}$ has density $D(\mathcal{A})$ and is sum-free. It follows from Proposition 6 that all members of $\bar{\mathcal{A}}$ are odd. If n were odd, then $\bar{\mathcal{A}}$ would contain both odd and even members, so we must have n even and \mathcal{A} a subset of the odd residue classes in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$. This completes the proof. \square

We are now ready to prove Theorem 2. For those n with $D^*(n) \leq \frac{2}{5}$, the result holds for any number κ , so assume that $D^*(n) > \frac{2}{5}$. Let $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ be a product-free, sum-free set with $D(\mathcal{A}) = D^*(n)$. By Proposition 9, we have that n is even and that \mathcal{A} is a subset of the odd residues modulo n . Suppose that k is an integer with $n \leq 2^k < 2n$. Let $N = 2^{2k}n$ and let \mathcal{B} be the set of positive integers of the form $2^j b$ where $j \leq k$ and $b \leq N/2^j = 2^{2k-j}n$, such there is some $a \in \mathcal{A}$ with $b \equiv a \pmod{n}$. Then the members of \mathcal{B} are in $[1, N]$ and

$$|\mathcal{B}| = \sum_{j=0}^k 2^{2k-j} |\mathcal{A}| = 2^k (2^{k+1} - 1) |\mathcal{A}| > \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) 2^{2k+1} |\mathcal{A}|. \tag{1}$$

We note that \mathcal{B} is product-free as a set of residues modulo N . Indeed, suppose $2^{j_i} b_i \in \mathcal{B}$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$ and

$$2^{j_1} b_1 2^{j_2} b_2 \equiv 2^{j_3} b_3 \pmod{N}.$$

Let $a_i \in \mathcal{A}$ be such that $b_i \equiv a_i \pmod{n}$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$. We have that a_1, a_2, a_3 are odd, and since n is even, this implies that b_1, b_2, b_3 are odd. Using $j_1 + j_2 \leq 2k$, $j_3 \leq k$ and $2^{2k} | N$, we have $j_1 + j_2 = j_3$. Hence $a_1 a_2 \equiv a_3 \pmod{n}$, a violation of the assumption that \mathcal{A} is product-free modulo n . We conclude that \mathcal{B} is product-free modulo N .

It now follows from Theorem 1.1 in [6] that for n sufficiently large,

$$|\mathcal{B}| \leq N \left(1 - \frac{c}{(\log \log N)^{1-\frac{\epsilon}{2}} \log^2(\log \log \log N)^{1/2}}\right).$$

Further, since N is of order of magnitude n^3 , we have that $\log \log N = \log \log n + O(1)$, and so for any fixed choice of $c_0 < c$ we have for n sufficiently large that

$$|\mathcal{B}| \leq N \left(1 - \frac{c_0}{(\log \log n)^{1-\frac{\epsilon}{2}} \log^2(\log \log \log n)^{1/2}}\right).$$

Thus, from our lower bound for $|\mathcal{B}|$ in (1) we have

$$|\mathcal{A}| < \frac{N}{2^{2k+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{c_0}{(\log \log n)^{1-\frac{\epsilon}{2}} \log^2(\log \log \log n)^{1/2}}\right).$$

Since $N/2^{2k+1} = n/2$, it follows that for any fixed $c_1 < c_0$ and n sufficiently large, we have

$$|\mathcal{A}| < \frac{n}{2} \left(1 - \frac{c_1}{(\log \log n)^{1-\frac{\epsilon}{2}} \log^2(\log \log \log n)^{1/2}}\right).$$

We thus may choose κ as any number smaller than $c/2$. This concludes the proof of Theorem 2.

4. Examples With Large Density

In this section we prove Theorem 3. We follow the argument in [5] with a supplementary estimate from [6]. Let x be a large number, let ℓ_x be the least common multiple of the integers in $[1, x]$ and let $n_x = \ell_x^2$. Then $n_x = e^{(2+o(1))x}$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$ so that $\log \log n_x = \log x + O(1)$. For a positive integer m , let $\Omega(m)$ denote the number of prime factors of m counted with multiplicity. Let $k = k(x) = \lfloor \frac{\epsilon}{4} \log \log n_x \rfloor$, let

$$\mathcal{D}'_x = \{d|\ell_x : d \text{ odd}, k < \Omega(d) < 2k\},$$

and let \mathcal{A} be the set of residues a modulo n_x with $\gcd(a, n_x) \in \mathcal{D}'_x$. Then \mathcal{A} is product-free (cf. Lemma 2.3 in [5]), and since n_x is even and every residue in \mathcal{A} is odd, we have that \mathcal{A} is sum-free as well. We shall now establish a sufficiently large lower bound on $D(\mathcal{A})$ to show that $D^*(n_x)$ satisfies the inequality in the theorem with $n = n_x$.

For $d \in \mathcal{D}'_x$, the number of $a \pmod{n_x}$ with $\gcd(a, n_x) = d$ is $\varphi(n_x)/d$, so that

$$D(\mathcal{A}) = \frac{\varphi(n_x)}{n_x} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}'_x} \frac{1}{d} = \frac{\varphi(n_x)}{n_x} \left(\sum_{\substack{d|\ell_x \\ d \text{ odd}}} \frac{1}{d} - \sum_{\substack{d|\ell_x \\ d \text{ odd} \\ d \notin \mathcal{D}'_x}} \frac{1}{d} \right). \tag{2}$$

We have

$$\sum_{\substack{d|\ell_x \\ d \text{ odd}}} \frac{1}{d} = \prod_{2 < p \leq x} \frac{p}{p-1} \cdot \prod_{\substack{2 < p \leq x \\ p^a \parallel \ell_x}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{a+1}}\right) \geq \prod_{2 < p \leq x} \frac{p}{p-1} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{x}\right)^{\pi(x)}$$

and, since $\varphi(n_x)/n_x = 2^{-1} \cdot \prod_{p|n_x, p>2} (1 - 1/p)$, we find that

$$\frac{\varphi(n_x)}{n_x} \sum_{\substack{d|\ell_x \\ d \text{ odd}}} \frac{1}{d} \geq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{x}\right)^{\pi(x)} \geq \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\pi(x)}{x}. \tag{3}$$

We now use (6.2) in [6] which is the assertion that

$$\sum_{\substack{P(d) \leq x \\ \Omega(d) \notin (k, 2k)}} \frac{1}{d} \ll \frac{(\log x)^{\frac{\epsilon}{2} \log 2}}{(\log \log x)^{1/2}}.$$

Here, $P(d)$ denotes the largest prime factor of d . Since this sum includes every odd integer $d|\ell_x$ with $d \notin \mathcal{D}'_x$, we have

$$\frac{\varphi(n_x)}{n_x} \sum_{\substack{d|\ell_x \\ d \text{ odd} \\ d \notin \mathcal{D}'_x}} \frac{1}{d} \ll \frac{\varphi(n_x)}{n_x} \cdot \frac{(\log x)^{\frac{\epsilon}{2} \log 2}}{(\log \log x)^{1/2}} \ll \frac{1}{(\log x)^{1-\frac{\epsilon}{2} \log 2} (\log \log x)^{1/2}},$$

where we use Mertens' theorem in the form $\varphi(n_x)/n_x = \prod_{p \leq x} (1 - 1/p) \ll 1/\log x$ for the last step. Putting this estimate and (3) into (2), we get

$$D(\mathcal{A}) \geq \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\pi(x)}{x} - \frac{c'}{(\log x)^{1-\frac{\epsilon}{2} \log 2} (\log \log x)^{1/2}}$$

for some positive constant c' . Using $\pi(x)/x \ll 1/\log x$ and $\log x = \log \log n_x + O(1)$, we have

$$D(\mathcal{A}) \geq \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\kappa^*}{(\log \log n_x)^{1-\frac{\epsilon}{2} \log 2} (\log \log \log n_x)^{1/2}}$$

for any fixed constant $\kappa^* > c'$ and x sufficiently large. Thus, $D^*(n_x)$ satisfies the condition of Theorem 3 for x sufficiently large, completing the proof.

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